

Are we using your Instagram content in our project?

" Visual Framing of Vaping: How Instagram Influencers Shape Perceptions of Vaping Through Images"

Purpose of the Project

Your Instagram content is being used for a project that aims to:

- Identify the frameworks influencers use when posting content about vaping/e-cigarettes on Instagram.
- This study is part of my doctoral dissertation, and this data will be used for my second article.

Why Are You Selected?

You are selected because:

- The study aims to research influencers who write about vaping/e-cigarettes. As an influencer, you have been chosen based on a ranking of the most popular Instagram profiles that publish content about vaping.

Who Is Responsible for the Project?

UiT The Arctic University of Norway is responsible for the personal data processed in the project.

What Does Your Participation Involve?

- The methods used for data collection include the analysis of one or more images published by you on Instagram in connection with vaping.

Brief Information About Privacy

We only use your information for the purposes described in this letter. The information is processed in accordance with privacy legislation.

Best regards,
Project Leader/Students
Bente Evjen Schønning

Read More:

Data Protection - How We Store and Use Your Data

The data (the images) will be captured and utilized as data of this study. To ensure security, the images will be stored within a system protected by a two-step authorization process.

The data will be deleted after the project is finished approx. August 2026

What Gives Us the Right to Process Your Data?

We process your personal data based on the arguments for exemption from information due to the disproportionate difficulty of informing and the high expected public nature.

It is very difficult to reach the individuals behind the profiles of the images that are very public due to their very high number of Instagram followers. The content of these profiles reaches children and young people in Norway (ungdata.no), influencing an upward trend in vaping. With more knowledge about this type of unregulated information, better health-promoting campaigns can be built targeting children and young people in Norway.

On behalf of UiT The Arctic University of Norway, Data Services at Sikt - The Knowledge Sector's Service Provider has assessed that the processing of personal data in this project meets the requirements of privacy legislation.

Further the use of images in this published paper is based on Norwegian Law Copyright Act §37, first and fourth paragraphs. We also invoke the right of quotation and refer to the InfoSoc Directive (EU), Article 5(3)(d), and the Berne Convention, Article 10(2). In Norway, this is regulated by the Copyright Act, Section 29.

Questions

If you have questions or wish to exercise your rights, contact:

- Bente Evjen Schønning at bente.evjen.schoning@uit.no or supervisor/project manager Torkjel Sandanger at torkjel.sandanger@uit.no
- The Data Protection Officer at UiT The Arctic University of Norway is Annikken Steinbakk. She can be contacted via email at personvernombud@uit.no or by phone at 77 64 69 52. If you have questions about how Data Services have assessed the project, you can contact them via email: personvertjenester@sikt.no, or by phone: 73 98 40 40.